

(Semi-)leptonic decays of D Mesons at BESIII

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Leptonic and semi-leptonic D decays at BESIII contribute the most precise experimental measurement of $|V_{cs(d)}|$ and form factor $f_{D_{(s)}}$ in the world based on 2.93 fb^{-1} and 3.19 fb^{-1} data taken at center-of-mass energies $\sqrt{s} = 3.773$ and 4.180 GeV, respectively. The largest samples at the mass threshold of the charmed hadrons $D_{(s)}$ also provide chances to extract form factors of some semi-electronic decays for the first time and together with the semi-muonic decays we could understand lepton flavour universality better.

1 Introduction

The ground-states of charmed hadrons, e.g., $D^{0(+)}$ [1–13], D_s^+ [14–18] and Λ_c^+ [19, 20], can only decay weakly. Precision measurements of charm (semi-)leptonic decays provide rich information to better understand strong and weak effects as shown in Fig. 1. BESIII produces these charmed hadrons near their mass thresholds; this allows exclusive reconstruction of their decay products with well-determined kinematics. For example, using $D \rightarrow \ell \nu_\ell$ ($\ell = e, \mu$), we perform the most accurate measurements of $f_D |V_{c\bar{q}}|$, which the extraction of Cabibbo-Kabayshi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix elements $|V_{cd(q)}|$ are essential inputs to constrain the unitarity of the CKM matrix and some first measurements of form factor $f_+^{D \rightarrow M}(0)$ by study semi-leptonic decay $D_{(s)} \rightarrow M \ell \nu_\ell$, where M is a meson. They are essential measurements to calibrate the theoretical calculation [21–39] like Lattice QCD, QCD sum rule, *etc.* for the heavy quark decays. The ratio of semi-muonic and -electronic decays provide an important test in the lepton flavour universality (LFU).

Figure 1 – Feynman diagrams for leptonic D decays (left) and semileptonic D decays to mesons (right).

2 Leptonic decays

In the Standard Model, D mesons decay into $\ell\nu_\ell$ via a virtual W^+ boson. The decay rate of the leptonic decays $D_{(s)}^+ \rightarrow \ell^+\nu_\ell$ can be parameterized by the $D_{(s)}^+$ decay constant $f_{D_{(s)}^+}$ via [40]

$$\Gamma(D_{(s)}^+ \rightarrow \ell^+\nu_\ell) = \frac{G_F^2}{8\pi} |V_{cd(s)}|^2 f_{D_{(s)}^+}^2 m_\ell^2 m_{D_{(s)}^+} \left(1 - \frac{m_\ell^2}{m_{D_{(s)}^+}^2}\right), \quad (1)$$

where G_F is the Fermi coupling constant, $|V_{cs}|$ is the quark mixing matrix element, m_ℓ and $m_{D_{(s)}^+}$ are the lepton and D^+ masses, respectively. Using the measured branching fractions (BF) of these decays, one can determine the product of $f_{D_{(s)}^+} |V_{cd(s)}|$. By taking the $f_{D_{(s)}^+}$, calculated in LQCD, or $V_{cd(s)}$, obtained from a global fit to other CKM matrix elements that assumes unitarity, the $|V_{cd(s)}|$ or $f_{D_{(s)}^+}$ can be obtained.

2.1 $D^+ \rightarrow \ell^+\nu_\ell$

This analysis is based on the 2.93 fb^{-1} data sample taken at the center-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s} = 3.773 \text{ GeV}$. With a total number of about 1.7×10^6 single tagged D mesons reconstructed ($K^+\pi^-\pi^-$, $K_S^0\pi^-$, $K_S^0K^-$, $K^+K^-\pi^-$, $K^+\pi^-\pi^-\pi^0$, $\pi^+\pi^-\pi^-$, $K_S^0\pi^-\pi^0$, $K^+\pi^-\pi^-\pi^-\pi^+$, and $K_S^0\pi^-\pi^-\pi^+$), we obtain 409 ± 21 signals for $D^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu$ decay shown in Fig. 2. The BF of $D^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu$ is $\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu} = [3.71 \pm 0.19(\text{stat}) \pm 0.06(\text{sys})] \times 10^{-4}$, and in conjunction with the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-maskawa matrix element $|V_{cd}|$ determined from a global Standard Model fit, it implies a value for the weak decay constant $f_{D^+} = [203.2 \pm 5.3(\text{stat}) \pm 1.8(\text{syst})] \text{ MeV}$ [15].

Figure 2 – The M_{miss}^2 distributions of the accepted candidates of $D^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu$. Description of each background events. The dots with error bars are data. The blue can be found on figure.

Figure 3 – Fit to the accepted $D_s^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu$ candidate events. The dots with error bars are data. The blue solid curve is the fit result. The red dotted curve is the fitted background.

BESIII also searches for the leptonic decay $D^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau$. The preliminary result of BF is $\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau} = 1.20 \pm 0.24(\text{stat}) \times 10^{-3}$. Combing $\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu}$, we obtain $R = \frac{\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau}}{\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu}} = 3.21 \pm 0.64$, which is consistent with the leptonic flavor universality in the SM prediction.

2.2 $D_s^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu$

The analysis of $D_s^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu$ [14] is based on the 3.19 fb^{-1} data sample taken at $\sqrt{s} = 4.178 \text{ GeV}$. Using 14 ST modes, $D_s^- \rightarrow K^+K^-\pi^-$, $K^+K^-\pi^-\pi^0$, $K_S^0K^-$, $\eta_{\gamma\gamma}\pi^-$, $\eta_{\pi^0}\pi^+\pi^-\pi^-$, $\pi^+\pi^-\pi^-$, $K_S^0K^+\pi^-\pi^-$, $K_S^0K^-\pi^+\pi^-$, $\eta'_{\eta_{\gamma\gamma}}\pi^+\pi^-\pi^-$, $\eta'_{\eta_{\rho^0}}\pi^-$, $K_S^0K_S^0\pi^-$, $K_S^0K^-\pi^0$, $K^-\pi^+\pi^-$ and $\eta_{\gamma\gamma}\rho^-$, we obtain signal yield of 1135.0 ± 33.1 by fitting the M_{miss}^2 as shown in Fig. 3. We obtain the most

precision measurement of $\mathcal{B}_{D_s^+ \rightarrow \mu^+ \nu_\mu} = [5.50 \pm 0.16(\text{stat}) \pm 0.15(\text{syst})]\%$ and $f_{D_s^+} = 252.9 \pm 3.7(\text{stat}) \pm 3.6(\text{syst})$.

3 Semi-leptonic decays $D \rightarrow M \ell^+ \nu_\ell$

In the SM, the weak and strong effects in SL D decays can also be well separated. Their differential decay rate can be simply written as

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dq^2} = \frac{\mathcal{B}_{D \rightarrow M \ell^+ \nu_\ell}}{\tau_{D(s)}} = X \frac{G_F^2}{24\pi^3} |V_{cs(d)}|^2 p_M^3 |f_+^M(q^2)|^2, \quad (2)$$

where X is a multiplicative factor due to isospin, which equals to 1/2 for the decay $D^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu_e$ and 1 for the other decays, G_F is the Fermi coupling constant, p_M is the meson momentum in the D rest frame, $f_+^M(q^2)$ is the form factor of hadronic weak current depending on the square of the transferred four-momentum $q = p_D - p_M$. Based on analyzing the dynamics of SL decays, one can obtain the product of $f_+^M(0)$ and $|V_{cd(s)}|$. The form factor $f_+^M(0)|V_{cs(d)}|$ can be extracted from a fit to the measured partial decay rates in separated q^2 intervals.

3.1 $D \rightarrow \bar{K}(\pi) e^+ \nu_e$

Using the same data as that of the measurement of $D^+ \rightarrow \mu^+ \nu_\mu$, BESIII has measured the BF of $D \rightarrow K(\pi) e^+ \nu_e$ [2, 3, 7]

$$\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow K_S^0 e^+ \nu_e} = [8.604 \pm 0.056(\text{stat}) \pm 0.151(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu_e} = [0.363 \pm 0.008(\text{stat}) \pm 0.005(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_{D^0 \rightarrow K^- e^+ \nu_e} = [3.505 \pm 0.014(\text{stat}) \pm 0.033(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_{D^0 \rightarrow \pi^- e^+ \nu_e} = [0.295 \pm 0.004(\text{stat}) \pm 0.003(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow K_L^0 e^+ \nu_e} = [4.482 \pm 0.027(\text{stat}) \pm 0.103(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (7)$$

and form factors [2, 3, 7] of $D \rightarrow K(\pi) e^+ \nu_e$

$$f_+^K(0)[D^+ \rightarrow K_S^0 e^+ \nu_e] = [0.7248 \pm 0.0041(\text{stat}) \pm 0.0115(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (8)$$

$$f_+^K(0)[D^0 \rightarrow K^- e^+ \nu_e] = [0.7368 \pm 0.0026(\text{stat}) \pm 0.0036(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (9)$$

$$f_+^\pi(0)[D^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu_e] = [0.6216 \pm 0.0115(\text{stat}) \pm 0.0035(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (10)$$

$$f_+^\pi(0)[D^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu_e] = [0.6372 \pm 0.0080(\text{stat}) \pm 0.0044(\text{syst})]\%, \quad (11)$$

$$f_+^K(0)[D^+ \rightarrow K_L^0 e^+ \nu_e] = [0.748 \pm 0.007(\text{stat}) \pm 0.012(\text{syst})]\%. \quad (12)$$

Figure 4, 5 and 6 shows the projections of form factor on the fit to partial decay rates of $D \rightarrow K(\pi) e^+ \nu_e$ except for $D^+ \rightarrow K_L^0 e^+ \nu_e$.

3.2 $D \rightarrow K^-(\pi) \mu^+ \nu_\mu$

Muon channels also provide a chance to improve the precision of measurement on form factor $f_+^K(0)$, and more important, recent tension of LFU between τ^+ and μ^+ [41–43] need improved understanding in charm sector. Using 2.93 fb^{-1} data at $\sqrt{s} = 3.773 \text{ GeV}$, the BF of $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \mu^+ \nu_\mu$ is measured to be $[3.413 \pm 0.019(\text{stat}) \pm 0.035(\text{syst})]\%$. Combining with $\mathcal{B}_{D^0 \rightarrow K^- e^+ \nu_e}$, we have

$$R_{K^-} = \frac{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow K^- \mu^+ \nu_\mu)}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow K^- e^+ \nu_e)} = 0.974 \pm 0.007(\text{stat}) \pm 0.012(\text{syst}), \quad (13)$$

Figure 4 – Projection on $f_+^K(q^2)$ for $D^0 \rightarrow K^- e^+ \nu_e$.

Figure 5 – Projection on $f_+^\pi(q^2)$ for $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^- e^+ \nu_e$.

Figure 6 – Projections on $f_+(q^2)$ for $D^+ \rightarrow \bar{K}^0 e^+ \nu_e$ (left) and $D^+ \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu_e$ (right) as function of q^2 , where the dots with error bars show the data and the lines give the best fits to the data with different form factor parameterizations.

where lifetime of D^0 is cancelled. With the same data and fitting method as previous electron channel, we obtain $f_+^K(0) = 0.7327 \pm 0.0039(\text{stat}) \pm 0.0030(\text{syst})$ [10]. Figure 7 shows the projection of form factor on the fit to partial decay rates. Combining with our previous measurement, LFU test is performed with

$$R_{K^-} = \frac{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow K^- \mu^+ \nu_\mu)}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow K^- e^+ \nu_e)} = 0.974 \pm 0.007(\text{stat}) \pm 0.012(\text{syst}). \quad (14)$$

There is no deviation larger than 2σ from 1 in q^2 interval (0.2, 1.5) GeV^2/c^4 as Fig 7 shows. For the pion channel, the BF of $D \rightarrow \pi \mu^+ \nu_\mu$ [12] is measured to be $\mathcal{B}_{D^0 \rightarrow \pi^- \mu^+ \nu_\mu} = [0.272 \pm 0.008(\text{stat}) \pm 0.006(\text{syst})]\%$ and $\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \pi^- \mu^+ \nu_\mu} = [0.350 \pm 0.011(\text{stat}) \pm 0.010(\text{syst})]\%$. Using these results along with $\mathcal{B}_{D \rightarrow \pi e^+ \nu_e}$, we have

$$R_{\pi^-} = \frac{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow \pi^- \mu^+ \nu_\mu)}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow \pi^- e^+ \nu_e)} = 0.922 \pm 0.030(\text{stat}) \pm 0.022(\text{syst}), \quad (15)$$

$$R_{\pi^0} = \frac{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow \pi^0 \mu^+ \nu_\mu)}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow \pi^0 e^+ \nu_e)} = 0.964 \pm 0.037(\text{stat}) \pm 0.026(\text{syst}). \quad (16)$$

These results show no significant deviations from the standard model predictions.

Figure 7 – The fit to the partial decay rates of $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \mu^+ \nu_\mu$ (up left), the projection to the hadronic form factor (up right) and LFU test in various q^2 intervals (right).

Figure 8 – Projections of the fits to partial decay rate of $D_s^+ \rightarrow \eta^{(l)} e^+ \nu_e$. Dots with error bars are data. Curves are the fits as described in text. Pink lines with yellow bands are the LCSR calculations with uncertainties.

3.3 $D_s^+ \rightarrow \eta^{(l)} e^+ \nu_e$

BESIII measure the absolute BF's for semi-leptonic $D_s^+ \rightarrow \eta^{(l)} e^+ \nu_e$ decays with improved precision. The preliminary results are $\mathcal{B}_{D_s^+ \rightarrow \eta e^+ \nu_e} = [2.32 \pm 0.06(\text{stat}) \pm 0.06(\text{syst})]\%$ and $\mathcal{B}_{D_s^+ \rightarrow \eta' e^+ \nu_e} = [0.82 \pm 0.07(\text{stat}) \pm 0.03(\text{syst})]\%$ by a simultaneous fits on $\eta \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ and $\eta\pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ for η mode and $\eta' \rightarrow \eta_{\gamma\gamma}\pi^+\pi^-$ and $\eta' \rightarrow \gamma\pi^+\pi^-$ for η' mode. Combing the our previous measurement on $\mathcal{B}_{D^+ \rightarrow \eta^{(l)} e^+ \nu_e}$ [11], the $\eta - \eta'$ mixing angle is determined to be $\phi_P = (40.2 \pm 1.4(\text{stat}) \pm 0.5(\text{syst}))^\circ$. And for the first time, the experimental measurement of the dynamics of $D_s^+ \rightarrow \eta^{(l)} e^+ \nu_e$ are performed, the products of the hadronic form factor $f_+^{\eta^{(l)}}(0)$ and $|V_{cs}|$ are extracted with different form factor parameterizations. Figure 8 shows the projection of form factor on the fit to partial decay rates, where the yellow band comes from Light cone sum rule [44]. For the two parameter series expansion, the preliminary results are $f_+^{\eta}(0)|V_{cs}| = 0.446 \pm 0.005(\text{stat}) \pm 0.004(\text{syst})$ and $f_+^{\eta'}(0)|V_{cs}| = 0.477 \pm 0.049(\text{stat}) \pm 0.011(\text{syst})$. Taking $|V_{cs}|$ from the CKMfitter as input, we determine preliminary $f_+^{\eta}(0) = 0.458 \pm 0.005(\text{stat}) \pm 0.004(\text{syst})$ and $f_+^{\eta'}(0) = 0.490 \pm 0.050(\text{stat}) \pm 0.011(\text{syst})$. Alternatively, using the $f_+^{\eta^{(l)}}(0)$ calculated by light-cone sum rules leads to $|V_{cs}| = 1.032 \pm 0.012(\text{stat}) \pm 0.009(\text{syst}) \pm 0.079(\text{theo})$ and $0.917 \pm 0.094(\text{stat}) \pm 0.021(\text{syst}) \pm 0.155(\text{theo})$, respectively.

Figure 9 – Comparison of $|V_{cs}|$.

Figure 10 – Comparison of $f_+^K(0)$.

3.4 $D_s^+ \rightarrow K^{0(*)} e^+ \nu_e$

Using the data sample collected at $\sqrt{s} = 4.178$ GeV, BESIII measured $D_s^+ \rightarrow K^{0(*)} e^+ \nu_e$ [18]. The preliminary results are $\mathcal{B}_{D_s^+ \rightarrow K^0 e^+ \nu_e} = [3.25 \pm 0.38(\text{stat}) \pm 0.16(\text{syst})]\%$ and $\mathcal{B}_{D_s^+ \rightarrow K^{0*} e^+ \nu_e} = [2.37 \pm 0.26(\text{stat}) \pm 0.20(\text{syst})]\%$. The first measurements of the hadronic form-factor parameters are obtained. The preliminary result for $D_s^+ \rightarrow K^0 e^+ \nu_e$ is $f_+^K = 0.720 \pm 0.084(\text{stat}) \pm 0.013(\text{syst})$, and for $D_s^+ \rightarrow K^{0*} e^+ \nu_e$, the preliminary form-factor ratios are $r_V = V(0)/A_1(0) = 1.67 \pm 0.34(\text{stat}) \pm 0.016(\text{syst})$ and $r_2 = A_2(0)/A_1(0) = 0.77 \pm 0.28(\text{stat}) \pm 0.07(\text{syst})$.

4 Summary

In summary, with the world's largest $D\bar{D}$ samples near threshold, precision measurements of BF's of $D_{(s)}^+ \rightarrow \ell^+ \nu_\ell$, $D \rightarrow \bar{K}(\pi) \ell^+ \nu_\ell$, $D_{(s)0}^+ \rightarrow \eta' e^+ \nu_e$ and $D_s^+ \rightarrow K^{0(*)} e^+ \nu_e$ are performed at BESIII. In these decays, the form factor of $f^{D_s \rightarrow \eta}$, $f^{D_s \rightarrow K^{0(*)}}$ are extracted for the first time. Besides, CKM absolute matrix $|V_{cs(d)}|$, D meson decay constant $f_{D_s^+}$ and hadronic form factor $f_+^{D \rightarrow K}$ are also determined.

Meanwhile, LFU test using (semi-)leptonic D decays is performed at BESIII, and no significant deviation from the SM prediction is found at current statistics.

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